

12/30/2014

REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

VOL III Issues VI

**NOV-DEC
2014**

***Electronic International Interdisciplinary
Research Journal (EIIRJ)***

Chief-Editor:

Ubale Amol Baban

ISSN : 2277-8721

Impact factor:0.987

www.aarhat.com

**WEB MEDIA – A BOON FOR GLOBAL SOCIETY THROUGH DISTANCE
LEARNING**

Research paper in Social Work

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Introduction –

Distance learning is a field of Education that focuses on the pedagogy and andragogy, technology and instructional systems design that aim to deliver education to students who are not physically 'On site'. Distance learning is the process to create and provide access to learning when the source of information and the learners are separated by time and distance. It is the process of creating an educational experience of equal qualitative value for the learner to best suit their needs outside the classroom. Thus web media or emerging technology is becoming widely used in universities and institutions around the global and getting international recognition.

Historical Background –

The University of London was the first to offer distance learning degrees in 1958. The society to encourage studies at home was founded in 1873 in Boston, Massachusetts. In 1911, in Australia, the University of Queensland established its Dept of correspondence studies. Another pioneering institution was the University of South Africa which run the courses since 1946. In

Newzeland, University level external study began in 1960 at Massey University. The largest Distance Education University in United Kingdom is the Open University founded in 1969. Spain's Public UNED was founded in 1972. In Germany the Fern University in Hagen was founded in 1974, later numerous institutions around the world have grown and become Mega Universities. The University of Chicago gave first extension service in America through Email. In India, it almost started when the Program of Action of the National Policy on Education in 1986 was declared. Indira Gandhi Open University and Y.C.M.O.U. Open University and other institutions started online courses throughout India. Many autonomous and deemed Universities are involving people in distance Education only through the web media and educational technology.

A statement made in 1987 in UNESCO Publication considered distance learning as 'only as a future prospect and scarcely yet a present reality', and suggested that perhaps in future distance learning systems and structures are inevitable part of every general education system.

A Shift from Technology to Learning:-

A web media has created exchange in all aspects of society. Students have to learn to navigate through large amount of information, to analyze and make decision and to master knowledge domains in an increasingly technological or global society.

- **Four Information Revaluation:-**

- I. Writing was invented 6000 years ago.
- II. First written book was published in 13000 B.C
- III. Invention of printing press in 1455 A.D.
- IV. The ICT revolution is the fourth informal revolution.

- **ICT Tools Resources:-**

- There are many tools of ICT for example
- Web based resources
- Electronic libraries
- Multimedia Resources
- Conferencing System

- **Varieties of ICT**

Video Discs

Printed Text

World Wide Web

Cable Television

Satellite Television

Computer- Controlled interactive Video

Internet- Facebook, Whats hap, Classblogs, Wikis etc.

- **Technologies of Two Groups**

Synchronous

A synchronous

Web Based

Audio cassettes

Telephone

Email

Mobile/Cell Phone

Message Board Forums

Video Conferencing

Print Materials

Direct Broadcast Satellite

Voice Mail

Internet

Fax

Radio

DVD

Live Streaming

Video Cassettes

Television

- **Features Of E- Learning**

- Its Dynamic
- Collaborative
- Operates in real Time
- Individual
- Comprehensive
- Computer Based
- Web-Based training
- Easily accessible
- Improve performance
- Increases Access
- Convenience

- Flexible For Users/ Learners

- **Changing Role Of a Teacher In Digital Age**

Sr. No.	Category	Attribute	Description A teacher Should be-
1	Pedagogical	Subject Matter Expert	Master of Subject and format content
2	Pedagogical	Mentor	Able to facilitate self learning.
3	Technical	Technology Friendly	Confortable with technology use.
4	Pedagogical	Course Designer	Good in Course Development and making a learner friendly interface.
5	Business	Service Oriented	To be fine as well as adhere to service quality expected in 24*7 environments.
6	Pedagogical	Community Builder	To creat seamless interaction and exchange
7	Business	Entrepreneur	To look for New opportunities.
8	Business	Team player	Egoless and able to work with team, of course developers, designers, student care, etc.

9.	Business + Pedagogy + Technical	Innovator	look for better technologies
10	Business	Agile	To adapt with changing needs of students/learners/society

A teacher needs to have these ten skills. He/she should get technically and equipped to manage the dilemma between customization and convenience of learner: On Line Education is now the need of an age.

Need to take Action / Suggestions

- Create and support a forum to connect distance educators, information technologists, policy makers and practioners for rethinking education.
- Support mechanism for the exchange of ideas and experiences in use of webmedies.
- Encourage explorations and experimentation of ICT for more effective learning.
- Encourage and engage in collaborate schemes for developing curriculum.
- Support the design of information infrastructure.
- Become familiar with the role and applications of web media / ICT.
- Develop an understanding the structure of on-line education.
- Develop a basic understanding of the technologies underlying information and ICT systems and approaches and technology management.
- Develop an appreciation for the challenge and opportunities in international interdisciplinary collaborative research.
- Develop research, analytic, writing, technology and presentation skills through collaborative research report writing and class presentation.
- In this global age and global society everybody is using web media for learning purpose and expanding their knowledge to cope with the digital world.

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